

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complexes of Zn (II), Hg (II) and Fe (III) Chlorides with α -Cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl Amino Aniline

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Spectrophotometric studies have been carried out on the chelates of Zn(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III) with α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline. The compositions and stability constants of these chelates have also been determined.

Anils containing auxochromic groups, give colour reactions on reacting with some metal ions. Attention to this fact was drawn for the first time by Krohnke and Gross.¹ The nature of the complexes of several Lewis acids formed with the anil obtained from *p*-bromophenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino aniline has also been thoroughly investigated earlier.² No work, however, seems to have been done on the chelates of metal ions with cyano aroyl anils in which the hydrogen atom of the azomethine group ($-\text{CH} = \text{N}-$) is substituted by a nitrile group. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the chelating properties of some of the cyano aroyl anils. The present communication deals with the spectrophotometric studies on the composition and stability of α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline with Zn(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III).

EXPERIMENTAL

*Preparation of α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline* : The compound was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of *p*-hydroxy acetophenone, iodine and pyridine for about an hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and acetone was then added. The pyridinium iodide thus obtained was dissolved in 50% alcohol at 20°, and treated with *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline³. To the reaction mixture was added a solution of 10% sodium cyanide and the product was kept in a freezing mixture overnight. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and crystallized from hot ethanol to afford reddish coloured crystals with a silky lustre (m.p. 150°).

Solutions of A.R. samples of the chlorides of Zn(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III) were prepared in spectroscopically pure methanol and their metal content was estimated gravimetrically. Stock solutions of the ligand were also prepared in methanol.

Nature of the Complex : To ascertain the proper wavelengths for studying various aspects of chelation, Vosburg and Cooper's method was employed using Bausch and Lomb spectronic '20' spectrophotometer. All the measurements were carried out at 30°. The

1. F. Krohnke and K. F. Gross, *Chem Ber.*, 1958, **92**, 36.
2. C. L. Taploo, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Roorkee, 1967.
3. A. I. Vogel, 'A text book of Practical Organic Chemistry', 1948, pp. 551, Longmans Green and Co.

λ max. of the ligand was found at $490\text{ m}\mu$ while in the complex, there was a bathochromic shift from these wavelengths to $590\text{ m}\mu$, $585\text{ m}\mu$ and $600\text{ m}\mu$ for Zn(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III) respectively. Hence, these wavelengths were chosen to study stoichiometry of the components by the following methods : (i) Job's method of continuous variation, (ii) Slope ratio method and (iii) Mole ratio method.

The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hrs' equilibration. The colour did not fade even after one week, revealing the stability of the chelates.

Stoichiometry of the components : In Job's method, varying volumes of metal ions were added to the required volumes of the ligand so that the final volumes of the species together remained constant. For example, 1, 2, 3 9 ml. of zinc chloride ($0.066 \times 10^{-3}M$) were taken and 9, 8, 7 1 ml. of the ligand ($0.066 \times 10^{-3}M$) were added in order to keep the final volume 10.0 ml. The systems studied are presented graphically in Fig. Nos. [1(a), 2(a) and 3(a)]. The peaks of the curves determine the composition of the chelates.

In slope ratio method, two sets of solutions were prepared. In one set, varying volumes of the metal ions were added to a constant volume of the ligand and vice-versa in the other set. The total volume was kept constant at 10.0 ml. by adding methanol. Their optical densities were measured and plotted against varying amounts of the metal ions as well as that of the ligand. The ratios of the slopes of the straight lines show the composition of the chelates. [Figs. 1(b), 1(c), 2(b), 2(c)].

Fig. 1 (b)

Fig. 1 (c)

Fig. 2 (b)

Fig. 2 (c)

In mole ratio method, various amounts of the ligand were added to the constant amount of the solution of the metal ions and vice-versa. The concentrations of the ligand and that of the metal ions were kept same. The curves were plotted between optical density and the different amounts of the metal ions and vice-versa Figs. 1(d).

Stability Constants: The apparent stability constants were calculated from the absorbance data using mole ratio method in the case of Zn(II) and Fe(III) complexes while continuous variation method using non-equimolar solutions in the case of Hg(II) complex.

a - 2 ml. of $0.66 \times 10^{-3} M Zn^{++}$, added $0.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ligand.
 b - 2 ml. of $0.55 \times 10^{-3} M Zn^{++}$, added $0.55 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ligand.

Fig. 1(d)

a → Concn. of $HgCl_2$ solu. - $0.625 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 Concn. of ligand - $0.416 \times 10^{-3} M$
 b → Concn. of $HgCl_2$ solu. - $0.66 \times 10^{-3} M$
 Concn. of ligand - $0.33 \times 10^{-3} M$
 Fig. 3(b)

Zn(II) and Fe(III) react with α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline according to the following equation :

c 0 0 (Initial concentration)

$c(1-\alpha)$ $\alpha.c$ $n\alpha.c$ (Final concentration)

c is the total concentration of the complex in moles per litre assuming no dissociation and α is the degree of dissociation.

Equilibrium constant K is given by :

$$K = \frac{(\alpha.c)(n\alpha.c)^n}{c(1-\alpha)}$$

The value of n for the complex has been established by different methods; α may be obtained from molar ratio curves by the following relationship :

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

Where E_m is the maximum extinction obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve, indicating that the whole of the metal ion is present in the form of a complex, E_s is the extinction at the stoichiometric molar ratio of the ligand to the metal in the complex.

Instability constant (K) as well as the stability constant (K') (where $K' = 1/K$) of Hg(II) complex is calculated from Job's equation :

$$K = \frac{(C^{m+n-1} P^{n-1} [(P_m + n)(x - n)]^{m+n}}{m^{n-1} n^{m-1} (P-1)^{m+n-1} [n - (m+n).X]}$$

Where c stands for the concentration of Hg(II) ions, Pc stands for the concentration of the ligand and X is the amount of the ligand used as determined from the maxima in the curves [Fig. 3(b)].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Zn(II) and Hg(II) were found to form 1 : 1 complex with stability constants 0.3373×10^7 and 0.404×10^5 respectively. However, Fe(III) forms a 1 : 2 (M : L) complex with stability constant 0.8871×10^7 .

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